

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Po'latov Otabek

XIX ASRNING 90-YILLARIDA HAZORALAR MILLIY QARSHILIK

HARAKATLARI

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